

Conformal Transformation and the Complex Potentials in Ideal Hydrodynamics

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Abstract.

This article was written to graduate and postgraduate students of physics and engineering. We show how complex functions, conformal transformation and complex potentials are used in hydrodynamics of ideal fluids. We have also briefly analyzed complex potentials in electrostatic.

Key words: complex functions; conformal transformations ;complex potentials.

(I)Introduction.

Complex functions, conformal transformation and complex potentials are very useful mathematical tools that can be used to describe many physical phenomenon like, Hydrodynamic and Heat flows, Elasticity, Gravitational Field, Electrostatics, Magnetism and Electric Current flows. Our paper is a didactical one written to students of physics and engineering showing how hydrodynamics problems can be studied using the theory of functions of complex variable. There are excellent text books on this subject but, to be concise, we will consider only the Irving and Mullineux book.^[1] In **Section 1** are defined *Analytic Functions*. In **Section 2** we present *Conformal Transformations* that connect complex planes. In **Section 3** are defined analytic functions, named *Complex Potentials*. In **Section 4** is seen how some *Hydrodynamic Flows* of ideal fluids can be studied using the analytic formalism defined above. In **Section 5** is shown the *Uniform Flow around a Plate*. In **Section 6** is seen the *Flow Around an Airfoil*. Finally, in **Section 7** we briefly show how *2-dimensional Electrostatic Problems* can be studied with the approach seen above.

(1) Function of a complex variable.

Let us consider a two 2-dimensional complex plane with variable $z = x + iy$ and an *analytic function* $\omega(z)$, expect at a finite number of singularities,^[1]

$$\omega(z) = f(z) = u(x,y) + i v(x,y) \quad (1.1),$$

where u and v obey the **Cauchy-Riemann equations**,^[1] that is,

$$\partial u/\partial x = \partial v/\partial y \quad \text{and} \quad \partial u/\partial y = -\partial v/\partial x \quad (1.2),$$

and the 2-dim Laplace equations,

$$\partial^2 u/\partial x^2 + \partial^2 u/\partial y^2 = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \partial^2 v/\partial x^2 + \partial^2 v/\partial y^2 = 0 \quad (1.3),$$

showing that $u(x,y)$ and $v(x,y)$ are harmonic functions, and $\omega(z)$:

$$d\omega(z)/dz = (\partial u/\partial x) + i(\partial v/\partial x) = (\partial v/\partial y) - i(\partial u/\partial y) \quad (1.4).$$

(2) Conformal transformation.^[1]

The equation (1.1), $w = F(z)$ connects two 2-dimensional complex planes with variables $z = x + iy$ and $\omega(z) = F(z) = u + i v$, respectively. It can be interpreted as mapping given locus in the z -plane into the locus in the ω -plane. It is possible to find a wide class of such transformation in which complicated loci in the z -plane are mapped into fairly simple ones in the ε -plane. It is by this method many problems of physics are solved.

Differentiation of the function $\varepsilon = F(z)$ gives

$$d\omega/dz = F'(z) \equiv \chi \exp(i\alpha) \quad (2.1),$$

where $\chi = |F'(z)|$ is supposed neither zero nor infinite. Equating the *moduli* and *phases* of each side of (2) we have

$$|d\omega| = \chi |dz| \quad \text{and} \quad ph(d\omega) = \alpha + ph(dz) \quad (2.2),$$

where $ph(\dots)$ means "phase" or "argument" of (...). Let us suppose that in the z -plane we have a curve (locus) Γ and that in the ω -plane the corresponding figure (locus) γ . Equations (2.2) mean that:

- (A) An infinitesimal arc of γ is χ times the corresponding arc of Γ , that is, the γ arc is **magnified** by χ factor χ and that the arc $d\varepsilon$ is turned through an angle α in the positive sense;
- (B) The phase angles under the transformation are **preserved** in magnitude and sense.

To see this we note that in the z -plane near P_1 we have $dz_2/dz_1 = F'(z_1)$, that is, $\theta_1 = ph(dz_2) - ph(dz_1) = ph[F'(z_1)]_{P_1}$ where θ_1 is the difference of angles of the respective dz 's. Similarly, in ω -plane $d\omega_2/d\omega_1 = F'(z_1)$, that is, $\theta_2 = ph(d\omega_2) - ph(\omega_1) = ph[F'(z_1)]_{P_1}$. where θ_2 is the difference of angles of the respective $d\omega$'s.

This complex transformation, at all nonsingular points, is said

to be **conformal**: under it infinitesimal figures in z -plane transform into similar, but re-oriented, figures in the ω -plane.

Note that the coordinate transformation between two manifolds is valid only when it is possible to obtain the inverse transformation. That is, when the Jacobian of the transformation does not vanish or it is not infinite. That is, if at a point $z = z_1$ ("critical point") of the curve Γ we have

$$|F'(z_1)| = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \infty \quad (2.3).$$

the transformation ceases to be conformal and no single-valued inverse of $\omega = F(z)$ exist. As $\omega = f(z)$ is assumed to be regular, u and v satisfy the Cauchy-Riemann equations. In this way, we verify that the Jacobian of the transformation is given by,

$$J(x,y,u,v) = (\partial u/\partial x)^2 + (\partial v/\partial x)^2 = |F'(z)|^2 \quad (2.4).$$

When $|F'(z)|^2 \neq 0$ or ∞ , the transformation is *conformal*.

As a consequence of the item (B), orthogonal families of curves $u(x,y) = \text{constant}$ and $v(x,y) = \text{constant}$ in the z -plane are also orthogonal families of curves in the ω -plane.

Note that if $\Phi(x,y) = \eta(x,y) + i \xi(x,y)$ is a solution of the Laplace equation, and if under the conformal transformation $F(z)$ it becomes $\Phi(\eta,\xi)$ then $\Phi(\eta,\xi)$ also satisfy the Laplace equation, that is,

$$\partial^2 \Phi(\eta,\xi)/\partial \eta^2 + \partial^2 \Phi(\eta,\xi)/\partial \xi^2 = 0 .$$

Example (2.1)

Straight lines $x = \text{constant}$ and $y = \text{constant}$ in the z plane and $F(z) = \cos(z)$.

So, writing

$\cos(z) = (e^{iz} - e^{-iz})/2 = (e^{ix-y} - e^{-ix+y})/2 = \cosh(y)\cos(x) + i \sinh(y)\sin(x)$,
that is, $\cos(z) \equiv u(x,y) + iv(x,y)$, where

$$u(x,y) = \cosh(y)\cos(x) \quad \text{and} \quad v(x,y) = \sinh(y)\sin(x). \quad (2.5).$$

From Eqs.(2.5) we get the following curves in the ω -plane:
 $u^2/\cosh^2(y) + v^2/\sinh^2(y) = 1$ and $u^2/\cos^2(x) - v^2/\sin^2(x) = 1$.
That is, curves with $x = \text{constant}$ in the z -plane become hyperboles in the ω -plane with focus in $u = -1$ and $u = 1$; curves in z -plane with $y = \text{constant}$ become ellipses with the same focus (Figure 1). We know from *analytical*

geometry that these conics with the same focus form a system of orthogonal curves.

Figure 1. Straight lines $x = \text{const}$ and $y = \text{const}$ in the z -plane and conformal figures in the ω -plane when $F(z) = \cos(z)$.

(3) Complex Potentials.

Let us define *Complex Potential* $\Omega(z)$ by the analytic function

$$\Omega(z) = F(z) = \phi(x,y) + i \psi(x,y) \quad (3.1),$$

where $\phi(x,y)$ and $\psi(x,y)$ are real *harmonic* functions that obey the relations seen in Sections 1 and 2. That is, $\partial\phi/\partial x = \partial\psi/\partial y$, $\partial\psi/\partial x = -\partial\phi/\partial y$ and $\Delta\phi(x,y) = \Delta\psi(x,y) = 0$, where $\Delta =$ Laplacian operator. If these functions represent orthogonal families of curves $\phi(x,y) = \text{constant}$ and $\psi(x,y) = \text{constant}$ in the z -plane they continue to be orthogonal families of curves in the Ω -plane defined by (3.1). Due to these peculiar properties very useful information are obtained interpreting physically these functions in various branches of applied mathematics in Physics. This is shown in the Table I.

TABLE I

	$\phi(x,y)$	$\psi(x,y)$
Hydrodynamics	Velocity potential	Stream function
Heat flow	Isothermals	Heat flow lines
Elasticity	Strain function	Stress lines
Gravitational field	Gravitational potential	} Lines of force
Electrostatics	} Potential	
Magnetism		
Current flow		

(4) Hydrodynamics.

Some of the most interesting applications of this theory are to problems of *ideal fluids hydrodynamics*,^[1,2] and so the tendency will be to interpret the *complex potential* applicable to this subject.

Indeed, in hydrodynamics a stream line is defined by a *stream function* $\psi(x,y)$ that obeys the conditions^[2]

$$V_x = \partial\psi/\partial y \quad \text{and} \quad V_y = -\partial\psi/\partial x, \quad (4.1)$$

where V_x and V_y are the components of the velocity of the stream parallel to the x and y axes, respectively. Along a stream line we have

$$d\psi = (\partial\psi/\partial x)dx + (\partial\psi/\partial y)dy = 0. \quad (4.2)$$

As, for an incompressible fluid $\text{div}(\mathbf{V}) = 0$ we see that \mathbf{V} can also be written in terms of a *velocity-potential* function $\phi(x,y)$:

$$V_x = \partial\phi/\partial x \quad \text{and} \quad V_y = -\partial\phi/\partial y. \quad (4.3)$$

From (4.1)-(4.3) we also verify that

$$\Delta\phi(x,y) = \Delta\psi(x,y) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{grad}(\phi) \cdot \text{grad}(\psi) = 0 \quad (4.4),$$

that is, ϕ and ψ are harmonic functions and that the *stream lines* (represented by a continuous lines) are orthogonal to the *velocity-potential* lines (represented by a dotted lines). Thus, in hydrodynamics the potential function $\Omega(z)$ is defined by

$$\Omega(z) = f(z) = \phi(x,y) + i \psi(x,y) \quad (4.5).$$

In the general case when we have uniform flows very far from immersed body the potential $\Omega(z)$ can be written as^[1,2]

$$\Omega(z) = A z + B \log(z) + \sum_n a_n/z^n \quad (3.2),$$

where A, B, a_n are complex numbers. Some simple cases of flow are discussed in what follows.

(4.1) $\Omega(z) = A z \rightarrow$ Uniform stream

Assuming the stream to be uniform, i.e. V_x and V_y to be constants

$$d\Omega/dz = \partial\phi/\partial x + i \partial\phi/\partial y = V_x - i V_y = \text{constant}$$

showing that $\Omega(z)$ is a linear function of z . That is,

$$V_o z \exp(i\alpha) = V_o (\cos \alpha + i \sin \alpha)(x + i y), \quad (4.7)$$

where V_o and α are real constants. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \phi &= V_o(x \cos \alpha - y \sin \alpha) \\ \psi &= V_o(y \cos \alpha + x \sin \alpha) \quad \text{and} \end{aligned}$$

$$V_x = \partial\phi/\partial x = V_o \cos \alpha \quad \text{and} \quad V_y = \partial\phi/\partial y = -V_o \sin \alpha .$$

So, we have an uniform flow with velocity V_o inclined at an angle α relative to the x-axis.

(4.2) $\Omega(z) = m \log(z) \rightarrow$ Point source ($m > 0$) and point sink ($m < 0$).

m is a real constant and $z = r \exp(i\theta)$. Then,

$$\phi = m \log r \quad \text{and} \quad \psi = m\theta \quad (4.8).$$

The curves when $\psi = \theta = \text{const}$ are the *streamlines*, i.e. they constitute a family of straight lines passing through the origin; the *equipotentials* $\phi = r = \text{const}$ are a family of dotted concentric circles, centre at the origin (Fig.2).

Figure 2. Point source when $m > 0$ and point sink when $m < 0$.

Since the stream function ψ measures the rate of flow across any curve, the **flow** Φ_γ across any curve γ encircling the origin is

$$\Phi_\gamma = \int_\gamma d\psi = \int_0^{2\pi} m d\theta = 2\pi m. \quad (4.9)$$

If $m > 0$ fluid is emanating from the origin at a rate equal to $2\pi m$ and we have a **point source** at the origin. If $m < 0$ we have a **point sink**. In either case m is called **strength**.

The **circulation** around the origin by curve γ is given by

$$C_\gamma = \int_\gamma d\phi = \int_\gamma m d(\log r) = 0 \quad (4.10)$$

since the value of $\log r$ returns to its original value on making a complete circuit of γ .

A point source or sink at a point $z = a$ is given by

$$\Omega(z) = m \log(z - a),$$

where $m > 0$ or $m < 0$, respectively.

(4.3) $\Omega(z) = -i \kappa \log(z) \rightarrow$ Point vortex.

κ real and $z = r \exp(i\theta)$.

So,

$$\phi = \kappa\theta \quad \text{and} \quad \psi = -\kappa \log(r) \quad (4.11);$$

the *streamlines* $\psi = \text{const}$ are concentric circles, centre the origin and the equipotential lines ϕ are dotted lines passing through the origin (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Point vortex with intensity κ counter clock horary.

As the stream function ψ measures the rate of flow across any curve, the **flow** Φ_γ across any curve γ encircling the origin is

$$\Phi_\gamma = \int_\gamma d\psi = - \int_\gamma \kappa d(\log(r)) = 0 \quad (4.12)$$

and the circulation

$$C_\gamma = \int_\gamma d\phi = \int_0^{2\pi} \kappa d\theta = 2\pi\kappa. \quad (4.13)$$

A **point vortex** at $z = \pm a$ is given by $\Omega(z) = -i \kappa \log(z \pm a)$.

(4.4) Superposition of flows.

Many examples of superposition of flows and figures can be seen, for instance, in reference [2]. Here only a few cases will be analyzed.

(4.4.1) Source + sink.

Source and sink at $z = \pm a$ are represented by the complex potential

$$\Omega(z) = \Omega_1(z) + \Omega_2(z) = m_1 \log(z - a) + m_2 \log(z + a),$$

where m_1 and m_2 can be positive or negative. In Figure 4 is shown a sink at $x = -a$ with intensity $m_1 = -m$ and a source 2 at $x = a$ with intensity $m_2 = m$.

Figure 4. Sink at $x = -a$ and source at $x = a$.

We have a "**dipole**" if $m_1 = m = -m_2$ or a "**doublet**" when $m_1 = m_2$.

(4.4.2) Dipole.

For a dipole we have:

$$\Omega(z) = m \log\left[\frac{z - a}{z + a}\right],$$

Then,

$$\phi = m \log\left|\frac{z-a}{z+a}\right| \quad \text{and} \quad \psi = m \operatorname{ph}\left[\frac{z-a}{z+a}\right].$$

When sink and source are very far apart, $|z| \rightarrow \infty$, $a \rightarrow 0$ and $m \rightarrow \infty$ (very large source) we verify that, putting $\mu = 2am$:

$$\Omega(z) = \lim\{m \log\left[\frac{z - a}{z + a}\right]\} = \lim\{m \log\left[\frac{1 - a/z}{1 + a/z}\right]\} \approx -\mu/z \quad (4.14)$$

In Electrostatic the point sink or source are replaced by line charges $q =$ charge per unit of length, and strengths m are replaced by $m = 2q/K$, where K is the dielectric constant of the medium:^[1]

$$\phi_{\text{elect}} = (2q/K) \log\left|\frac{z-a}{z+a}\right| \quad \text{and} \quad \psi_{\text{elect}} = m \operatorname{ph}\left[\frac{z-a}{z+a}\right].$$

(4.4.3) Sink + uniform stream.

If the flow is parallel to the x -axe that is, $\alpha = 0$ (See **Section 4.1**):

$$\Omega(z) = -V z - Q \log(z),$$

so,

$$\phi(x,y) = -V|z| - m \log|z| = -V x - Q \log[x^2 + y^2]$$

and $\psi(x,y) = -V \phi(z) - Q \phi(z) = -Vy - Q \tan^{-1}(y/x)$.

The streamlines that are given by [2]

$$\psi(x,y) = \text{const} = -V y - Q \tan^{-1}(y/x), \quad \text{seen in Figure 5,}$$

Fig. I.63

Figure 5. Superposition of sink with intensity Q and uniform stream with velocity V .

(4.4.4) Uniform flow + vortex + dipole.

The complex potential $\Omega(z)$ for the combination of an **uniform flow** with velocity V_0 in the negative x direction, point **vortex** and a **dipole** both situated at the origin $x = a = 0$ is given by, from Eqs.(4.7),(4.9) and (4.11),

$$\Omega(z) = -V_0 z - i \kappa \log(z) - \mu/z \quad (4.15).$$

If $z = r \exp(i \theta)$ the streamlines are given by $\psi = \text{Im}[\Omega(z)]$:

$$\psi(r,\theta) = \text{const} = -V_0 r \sin \theta - \kappa \log r + \mu \sin \theta / r \quad (4.16).$$

Let us define a number a given by $\mu = V_0 a^2$ substituting this value in (4.16) and putting $\text{const} = -\kappa \log a$, we have

$$V_0 r \sin \theta (r - a^2/r) + \kappa \log r = \kappa \log a \quad (4.17).$$

In this way, it is immediate that if $r = |z| = a$, then Eq.(4.17) is identically true for all values of θ . Detailed stream lines will not be shown here. So, the stream line $|z| = a$ is a circle centre the origin radius a (Figure 6); that is, one streamline is replaced by a rigid circular boundary, which can be taken to represent, for instance, the cross section of an infinite cylinder situated in the fluid. So, $\Omega(z)$ is the complex potential for a flow past an infinite cylinder situated in an uniform stream when a circulation around a vortex, given by Eq.(4.13), $2\pi\kappa$ is present. The potential $\phi(x,y)$ is given by [1]

$$\phi(x,y) = \text{Re}[\Omega(z)] = -V_0 x + \kappa \tan^{-1}(y/x) - \mu x/(x^2+y^2) \quad (4.18).$$

With the fluid velocities, $V_x = \partial\phi/\partial y$ and $V_y = -\partial\phi/\partial x$, one can estimate the force F_x and F_y (Figure 6) due to an ideal fluid on the cylinder taking into account the *Bernoulli's equation*.^[1,2] We have $F_x = 0$ and $F_y = 2\pi\rho\kappa V_0$ which is the *lifting force* called known as the *Kutta-Joukowski law*.^[2]

Figure 6. The stream lines are omitted. We have shown only the lifting force exerted by the fluid on the cylinder estimated using the Kutta-Joukowski law.^[1,2]

(5) Uniform flow around a plate.

Let us see the application of the above theory in the case of a plate with length d immersed in a uniform flow in the z -plane (Figure 7). In this figure is also shown, in the ϵ -plane, the flow around a circumference with radius a .

Figure 7. Illustration of the method used to estimate the flow around a plate using the conformal transformation.^[2]

As this flow is extremely difficult to obtain in the **z-plane** using directly the hydrodynamic Euler's equation it will be determined taking into account a conformal transformation, supposing that the flow conditions very far from the contours in the ε and z -planes are the same. This is done in two steps:

(I) First, using Euler's equation we determine in the **ε -plane** the flux $\Omega(\varepsilon)$ around a circumference with radius $a = 1$. This is would be given by ^[2]

$$\Omega(\varepsilon) = C(\varepsilon e^{-i\alpha} + e^{i\alpha}/\varepsilon) \quad (5.1),$$

where C is an adjustable parameter.

(II) Once known $\Omega(\varepsilon)$ we get the flux $\Omega(z)$ in the z -plane using a conformal transformation^[2]

$$\varepsilon \rightarrow z = F(\varepsilon) = (d/2)(\varepsilon + 1/\varepsilon) \quad (5.2),$$

which transforms the circumference with unitary radius in a plate with length d when ε varies along the circumference.

Putting $\Omega^* = \Omega[\varepsilon(z)]$ we have

$$d\Omega^*/dz = (d\Omega(\varepsilon)/d\varepsilon) (d\varepsilon/dz) = A(e^{-i\alpha} - e^{i\alpha}/\varepsilon^2)(d\varepsilon/dz) \quad (5.3).$$

Using (5.2) we obtain $\varepsilon(z) = z/d \pm [(z/d)^2 - 1]^{1/2}$. Since we must consider only points outside the plate ($|\varepsilon| \geq 1$) it is enough to take only the signal + of the square root. In this way, $d\varepsilon/dz = 2\varepsilon^2/(\varepsilon^2-1)d$. In this way, we get

$$d\Omega^*(z)/dz = [2C/d]\{(\varepsilon^2 e^{-i\alpha} - e^{i\alpha})/(\varepsilon^2-1)\} \quad (5.4).$$

Since for $\varepsilon \gg 1$ (very far from the origin) we must have^[2]

$d\Omega^*(z)/dz = v_x(z) - i v_y(z) \approx V e^{-i\alpha}$ we verify that $(2C/d) = V$. Consequently,

$$d\Omega^*(z)/dz = v_x(z) - i v_y(z) = V \{(\varepsilon^2 e^{-i\alpha} - e^{i\alpha})/(\varepsilon^2-1)\} \quad (5.5).$$

Using Eq.(5.5) the field velocity can be completely determined:

$$v_x(z) = V \cos(\alpha)/[z^2 - d^2]^{1/2} \quad \text{and} \quad v_y(z) = V z \sin(\alpha)/[z^2 - d^2]^{1/2} \quad (5.6),$$

showing the "critical points" $x_- = -d$ and $x_+ = d$, where the conformal transformation is invalid. This velocity flux is seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Illustration of the method used to estimate the stream lines (a) around a plate using the conformal transformation.^[2] In Figure (b) is shown the force of the fluid on the plate that are estimated in reference [2].

(6)Flow around airfoil submitted to an external uniform flux.

In the general case,^[2] the flow around an airfoil submitted to an uniform flux can be obtained using a conformal transformation slightly different from that seen in **Section 5**. It transforms circumferences in airfoils profiles of birds or airplanes. In the \$z\$-plane with coordinates \$(x,y)\$ and origin \$O\$ (**Figure 9**), a circular cylinder with radius **a** is immersed in an uniform flow with velocity **V**. The circle with radius **a** is centered at the point \$O_1\$ taken as the origin of an auxiliary coordinate system \$(x_1,y_1)\$.

Figure 9. Illustration of conformal transformation to analyze flow around airfoils.

(6.a) Flow with no vortices around the cylinder.

In this case, the airfoil profiles in \$\epsilon\$-plane from circumferences in \$z\$-plane are usually obtained using conformal transformations,^[2]

$$\epsilon = F(z_1) = z_1 + a_1/z_1 + a_2/z_1^2 + a_3/z_1^3 + \dots$$

In the particular case of \$A = 1, B = 0, a_1 = a^2\$ and \$a_2 = a_3 = \dots = a_n = 0\$ (\$n \geq 1\$) we have the *Joukowski transform*,^[2] that is, \$\epsilon(z_1) = z_1 + a^2/z_1\$, taken

into account in **Section 5**. So, we can show^[2] that in the z_1 -plane we have $\Omega(z_1) = -V(z_1 + a^2/z_1)$ around the cylinder. Thus, the flow around the airfoil in the ε -plane can be determined^[2] taking into account that $\varepsilon = z_1 + a^2/z_1$.

(6.b) Flow with vortices around the cylinder.

If there is a vortices with intensity Γ around the cylinder^[2](see **Section 4.3**) we get $\Omega(z_1) = -V(z_1 + a^2/z_1) - i(\Gamma/2\pi)\ln z_1$.^[2]

The resulting stream lines for the cases **(6.a)** and **(6.b)** are shown, respectively, in **Figures (9.a)** and **(9.b)**. Note that in **Fig.9** the incident flux V and the vortex orientation Γ are inverted, that is, $V \rightarrow -V$ and $\Gamma \rightarrow -\Gamma$.

Figures (9.a) and (9.b). Streamlines around airfoils when $\Gamma = 0$ (a) and $\Gamma \neq 0$ (b).

We can shown^[2] that the resulting forces ("drag forces") on the airfoils are equal to $F_a = 0$ and $F_b = F_L = \rho V \Gamma$ ("lift force"), where ρ is the fluid density.

(7) Two-dimensional electrostatic problems.

The method of *complex variable potential* combined with *conformal transformation* is also an especially powerful method of solving two-dimensional electrostatic problems.^[3] In this case the complex potential $\Omega(z)$, with $z = x + iy$, is written, following Panofsky & Phillips^[3] as

$$\Omega(z) = \Phi(x,y) + i \psi(x,y) \quad (7.1),$$

where $\Phi(x,y)$ is the electrostatic potential and $\psi(x,y)$ are the "stream functions" connected with electric field $\mathbf{E} = -\text{grad}(\Phi)$. The analytic function $\Omega(z)$ satisfy the Cauchy-Riemann relations

$$\partial\psi/\partial x = -\partial\Phi/\partial y \quad \text{and} \quad \partial\psi/\partial y = \partial\Phi/\partial x \quad (7.2),$$

and, consequently, $\text{grad}(\Phi) \cdot \text{grad}(\psi) = 0$ and $\Delta\Phi(x,y) = \Delta\psi(x,y) = 0$ where $\Delta = \text{Laplacian operator}$.

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